

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

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Sample Name: Proszki

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Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

- C K
- O K
- SiK

C K_ROI (66)

O K_ROI (27)

Si K_ROI (61)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 14.54 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	26.3	0.05	44.2	1070.6	10.2
O K	5.3	0.02	6.7	872.3	7.3
Si K	68.4	0.02	49.1	8482.2	5.6